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(Effect of Virtual-Field-Trip Strategy on Achievement in Pollution Concept among ... Adamu, B... Et. al. 2025)

Effect of Virtual-Field-Trip Strategy on Achievement in Pollution Concept among Secondary School Biology Students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigates the Effect of Virtual-Field-Trip Strategy on achievement in pollution concept among secondary school Biology Students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State, Quasi experimental research type was adopted for the study, specifically, the non-randomized pre-test, post-test control group design involving experimental and control groups. The population of the study consists of 372 SS 1 students from 4 Public schools in Gusau Metropolis, comprising 224 boys and 148 girls. A purposive sampling technique was used to obtain two public schools with comparable characteristics. The sample of the study consisted of 102 students from two intact classes selected. A reliability coefficient of 0.79. The study used descriptive statistics for data analysis, Percentages, mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions. The Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS) version 23 software was used to analyze the data collected. The findings revealed among others that senior secondary school students taught pollution using VFT achieved higher than those taught with traditional instruction. And male students when taught using virtual field trips outperformed their female counterparts. One of the recommendations from the study state that, state government should endeavor to equip all secondary schools within the state with resources needed for virtual learning environments.

Keywords; Virtual Field Trips, Achievement, Pollution Concept, Students, Gender.

Introduction

In order to give students, the tools they need to succeed in the modern world of science and technology, the Federal Government of Nigeria, emphasizes the importance of science education which is the cornerstone of any country's technological advancement and taught at all educational levels thereby making it mandatory at both primary and junior secondary schools. As a discipline, Science covers a wide range of areas such as biology, chemistry, and physics. In schools it can be taught as a combined subject as it is in elementary school or as a subject matter class as it is in later years, like biology. Bichi (2019) highlights that "At tertiary level, biology is one of the important subjects that formed part of the requirement for admission especially in pure and social sciences programs and it is part of general studies (science technology and society) for students in many fields of studies in Nigerian colleges of education, polytechnics and universities".

Biology, as the study of life encompasses a vast array of interconnected systems and processes. From the microscopic level of cell to the global scale of ecosystems, living organism's interacting with their environment in complex and dynamic ways. However, human activities have disrupted these natural systems leading to a range of environmental problems including pollution. Environment pollution has become one of the most pressing issues of contemporary time, affecting every aspect of the natural world and human health. It refers to the contamination of the Earth's environment with materials that interfere with human health, the quality of life, and the natural functioning of ecosystems. World Health Organization (2017) asserts that this phenomenon is largely the result of human activities, including industrial production, vehicle emissions, and the improper disposal of waste, contributing to a host of environmental problems.

There is a need therefore, to improve students' interest in biology through the use of appropriate teaching strategies that effectively convey the significance of environmental issues and the consequences of pollution on the environment and human health. This is because; one primary function of biology teaching is to help students understand its concepts, principles, theories and laws. Thus, the professional teacher is expected to give useful and meaningful instruction to his/her students so as to educate them properly for the general benefit of the nation (Zumyil, 2019). However, Dorgu (2015) pointed out that good teachers follow no one method, instead they use whatever methods or materials that appear best for the particular combination of individual situations, so that students would be able to learn more, retain more, and apply what is learnt by engaging in significant activities.

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However, some science educators including Agboghroma (2009), Ok (2009) and Lawal (2012), have stated that the attention of scientists and science educators has been focused on how to improve science instruction in schools. Okoye (2014) asserts that teaching has gone beyond the teacher standing in front of the learners to disseminate information to them without the learners' active participation in learning activities. Similarly, Akinbobola and Afolabi (2010) state that the challenge in teaching is to create experiences that actively involve students and support their thinking, explanation, communication and application of the scientific models needed to make sense of these experiences. There has been therefore significant shift of emphasis in science teaching from traditional content and factual acquisition of scientific knowledge to those which make students actively involved in learning science by doing. Ukpai (2014) suggests that biology which is a practical subject requires the use of practical approach to teach its concepts so as to produce students that would be able to acquire necessary knowledge, skills and competences that are needed to meet the scientific and technological demands of the society.

The world as a global community lays much emphasis on science and technology. The acquisition of science and technology at all levels of education depends on the teaching effectiveness measured in terms of the knowledge of what to teach, how to teach and when to teach it (Oyegun, 2013). In today's era of science and technology, there is a great need to improve quality of education especially science education. This can be possible by bringing fundamental changes through ICT driven innovative teaching and learning strategies that can provide students centered learning environment which makes learning processes more interesting to the students (Tafa, et al 2020). The rapid growth of technology in schools and its integration into teaching reshaped the interaction of teachers, students, curricula and technologies, and eventually transformed the learning environment (Ugur, 2019). The use of technology in science laboratories provides useful opportunities for students who can participate in high-budget, dangerous and complex experiments which are difficult to realize (Akçayır, et al, 2016). Building upon this recognized need for innovative ICT-driven strategies in science education, one particularly promising tool is the virtual field trips (VFT).

Captivating the 21st-century learner is a challenge, one that can be approached with the integration of various technologies to grasp the learner's interest. Virtual Field Trips (VFT) are one of such technology that has been integrated into the classroom. VFT is a guided exploration through the World Wide Web that organizes a collection of pre-screened, thematically based web pages into a structured online learning experience. (Foley,2017). According to Khotima, et al, (2021), Virtual Field Trip (VFT) is a collection of technology-based resources used together to give students the learning experience gained from an Actual Field Trip. It may be comprised of images, animations, audios and videos. Newsome,

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(2013) define virtual field trip (VFT) as alive interactive programmed and activities taught by a content provider to a classroom through the use of video conferencing technology. Spicer and Stratford cited in Zakareya (2019) define the VFT as "the integration of text, audio, graphics, still image and moving pictures into a single, computer-controlled multimedia product. Cox & Su cited in Lawal (2017) describe virtual field trip as a guided and narrated electronic tour that have been selected by educators and arranged in a thread of programmed that students can follow from site to site with just the click of a single button. It is a technology-based experience that allows students to take an educational journey without leaving the classroom. Virtual field trips offer immersive and interactive learning experiences that can stimulate real world environment and phenomena (Ejeh et al (2021). According to Opalewski and O'Leary (2019) unlike traditional methods, VFTs have the potential to overcome the challenges associated with teaching abstract concepts like pollution by providing students with visual and experimental encounters that make the unseen more tangible and understandable.

Gender is one of such factors also mentioned in various research studies to have considerable influence on students' academic achievement especially in science subjects (Kauru 2010: Amoo, 2011). It refers to the social cultural and psychological dimensions of being female or male. Whereas gender roles are the expectations that prescribe how males and females should think and behave which can influence student's response to learning. (Ogunkele & Umoru, 2017). Gender inequality in science and education in general has remained a persistent problem of global scope (Tile, 2013). The differences between boys and girls in relation to biology interest, have received a lot of attention. This is because it appears that there is still a considerable bias against female students which hinders their full participation in science education. However, one of the national objectives of education as spelt out in the National Policy on Education (2014) is to develop a Nigerian with bright opportunities to be made available for male and female students as to attain maximum potentials in education. In order to achieve this objective, appropriate teaching strategies are expected to be employed by teachers to balance the differences in student's outcomes. Therefore, inconsistencies in gender differences in academic outcome in biology calls for further investigation which is one of the concerns for this study. Therefore, this study investigates the effectiveness of virtual field trip in enhancing secondary school student's achievement of pollution concepts in Gusau Metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

Environmental pollution has become a critical global issue that has detrimental effects on both human health and the environment; it is the contamination air, water or soil leading to imbalance in the natural ecosystem. According to World Health Organization 2018 estimate, air pollution is the biggest environmental health risk and its responsible for about

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7million pre matured death annually due to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, water pollution is widespread with nearly about two billion or a quarter of the world population drink contaminated water on a daily basis, leading to waterborne diseases and destruction of aquatic ecosystem. To address this pressing issue and poster environmental literacy among future generations, there is need to equip our secondary school students with knowledge, skills and values necessary to understand the causes and the effect of environmental pollution, particularly within the educational context of Gusau Metropolis. This is significant because effectively conveying the complexities and often unseen nature of pollution to secondary school students can be a challenging with traditional pedagogical approaches. Therefore, exploring innovative and engaging 21st century learning is important to provide students with necessary understanding and skills to create sustainable solution for a healthier planet.

Research Objectives

The objective of this study was set to;

1. Determine the effect of virtual field trip on student's achievement in pollution concepts.
2. Determine the effect of virtual field trip on male and female student's achievements scores in pollution concept.

Research Question

1. What are the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught pollution concept using virtual field trips and those taught with traditional instruction?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female secondary school students taught pollution concept using virtual field trips?

Methodology

The quasi-experimental research type was adopted for the study, specifically, the non-randomized pre-test, post-test, control group design. The population of the study consisted of 372 SS 1 students from 4 Public schools in Gusau metropolis. The population comprised 224 boys and 148 girls. The sample of the study consisted of 102 students from 2 intact classes from 2 public schools in Gusau Metropolis. Out of the 2 schools, one was used as experimental group and the other school as the control group. Purposive sampling technique was used to obtain 2 public schools with comparable characteristics in Gusau Metropolis. The 2 sampled schools were randomly assigned to experimental and control groups. The treatment lasted for five weeks. One instruments title Pollution achievement test was used for collecting data. Two experts in biology education and one from measurement and evaluation validated the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha method and a coefficient of 0.82 was obtained, indicating excellent reliability, because according to Ali (2006) cited in Zumyil (2019), any

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instrument with reliability co-efficient between 0.7 to 0.99 is deemed reliable. The study used descriptive statistics for data analysis, Percentages, mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions. The Statistical Product for Service Solution (SPSS) version 23 software was used to analyze the data collected.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What are the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught pollution concept using virtual field trips and those taught with traditional instruction?

This research question was answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The result of the analysis is presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: Pre-test Post-test Mean and Standard Deviation achievement Scores of Students Taught pollution concepts Using Virtual Field Trips and Those Taught Using Traditional Teaching Approach

Teaching Method	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Diff
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	
Virtual Field Trip	52	68.04	9.58	80.91	12.17
Traditional teaching Approach	50	66.03	9.62	72.83	5.50

Table 1 shows that the post-test mean and standard deviation scores for the students taught using virtual field trip teaching approach are 80.91 and 7.98 while pre-test achievements mean and standard deviation scores of those taught with traditional approach are 66.03 and 13.93 respectively. The differences in the mean post-test achievement scores revealed that students taught pollution concepts with virtual field trip VFT achieved higher than those taught with traditional instruction. There is also reduction in standard deviation in the experimental group results showing overall achievement of the group.

Research Question Two: What are the mean achievement scores of male and female secondary school students taught pollution concept using virtual field trips?

This research question was answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The result of the analysis is presented in table below.

Table 2: Pre-test Post-test Mean and Standard Deviation achievement Scores of male and female secondary school students' taught pollution concepts using Virtual Field Trip.

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Pre-test	Post-test					
	N	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Mean Diff
Male	27	12.91	3.37	21.81	6.13	8.09
Female	25	12.76	4.82	20.53	6.35	7.77

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation scores of male and female student's achievements taught pollution using virtual field. The mean achievement scores of male students on pre-test and post-test are 21.81 and 8.09 while that of the female students are 20.53 and 7.77 respectively. This shows that at both pre-test and post-test of the male students performed better than the female students. Also, the differences in the mean post-test achievement scores revealed that male students outperformed their female counterparts.

Discussion of Results

The discussion of results of this study is based on the research questions of this study.

Effects of Virtual Field Trip Teaching Approach and Traditional Teaching Approach on Students' Achievement in Pollution Concepts

The finding from research question one revealed that students taught pollution concepts using Virtual field trip achieved better than their counterparts taught using a traditional teaching approach. This study's results align with the study of Sulaiman (2024) research who found significant differences between the achievement of experimental group and the control group in favor of experimental group. This conforms with the study of Thelma et al, (2024) who found that application of virtual reality technology in biology is more effective than the use of conventional teaching method, because VRT increases knowledge of the topic, promote active experience, rather than just passive information as it is done in conventional learning. This finding concurred with the findings of Harris and Osman (2015), who similarly reported that students taught using VFTs achieved higher academic outcomes compared to those taught with conventional field trip methods. This superior performance is likely attributable to the unique opportunities VFTs afford, such as enabling students to explore geographically distant environments like mangrove ecosystems. In addition, the use of VFT could provide an opportunity for students to explore the mangrove ecosystem not in their area, sees a graphical display and video clearly which help to improve their achievement in the topic of Colonization and Succession in Mangrove

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Ecosystems. The finding gains further support from the work of Karl (2014) who found that, while VFT appears to be a successful and innovative use of technology in the classroom, it also has direct cause of students' academic improvement. The positive impact of virtual learning environments on student achievement in biology is also consistently demonstrated by Gambari (2017) who reveals that "students exposed to physics practical's using a virtual laboratory package performed better than those with conventional laboratory methods. However, beyond academic gains, the convenience and flexibility offered by virtual learning platforms are significant advantages. This is evident in Gilman's (2006) study who found that "students written responses about the use of a virtual laboratory in teaching cell division noted the convenience of virtual laboratories and going at their own pace. These aspects of VFTs not only facilitate access to otherwise inaccessible content but also empower students with greater autonomy in their learning journey, further reinforcing their pedagogical value.

Influence of gender on students' achievement in Biology

The findings from research question two revealed that male students achieve better than their female counterparts. This finding agrees with the findings of Gidado et al (20) who found a significance difference in academic achievement of biology education students when exposed to virtual learning in favor of male students. This observed disparity aligns with Olumide (2015) study who similarly found superior male achievement in biology when utilizing computer simulation packages stressing a potential pattern of male advantage in technology-enhanced science learning environments. This finding is in contrast with the findings of Sulaiman (2024); Etim et al (2016), who's studies found that virtual learning environment is gender friendly. However, the finding gains further support from the work of Hatem (2023) found that in their virtual reality (VR) field trip context, gender did not exhibit any noteworthy impact on learning outcomes, also noting that such interventions can augment student engagement and mitigate discrepancies in resource accessibility. This finding also agrees with the findings of Yakubu et al, (2025) who investigate the effects of video-aid-simulation on students' performance in human circulatory system and found no gender influence. This notable divergence among studies, including the present study, intensely suggests that the influence of gender on academic achievement is not universal. Instead, it is highly mediated by specific factors such as the instructional method employed (virtual field trips vs. other pedagogies, the subject matter, the particular design and features of the learning technology, and even the socio-cultural context of the learners.)

Conclusion

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Based on the findings of the study, it can be deluded that Virtual Field Trips approach impacts more positively on achievement of students compared to traditional teaching approach. However, the findings of the present study have further reaffirmed the results from previous study which suggest that, VFTs enhanced academic achievement of senior secondary students toward pollution concepts. Teachers must therefore restrain from traditional approach of teaching and embrace the use of VFTs to enhance the cognitive level of students.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should try to apply the virtual learning instruction in the teaching of biology as this was found to impact on students' achievement positively and male and female should be equally engaged in the Virtual learning so as to eliminate gender bias.
2. The use of traditional teaching approach should be reduced to the barest minimum.
3. State government and stakeholders should endeavor to equip all secondary schools within the state with resources needed for virtual learning environment.
4. Workshops should be organizing for secondary school teachers to be enlightened on the relevance of entering into virtual learning.

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